

IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR INCREASING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *The given article presents the innovative development of the construction industry, as well as its economic mechanisms, which scientifically substantiates the fundamentals of innovative development.*

Keywords: *construction industry, urbanization, cement, tiles, metal tiles, slate, nodulin, roofing felt.*

It is important to mention that the growth of digitalization and integration of the economies of the world increases the need for the level of use of innovative activity of enterprises and its effective management. At present time it is necessary to effectively increase innovative activity not only at the country level, but also at the enterprise level. One of the main tasks in this direction is to achieve innovative potential that ensures the optimal development and functioning of modern enterprises for the production of building materials in a constantly changing external environment. Increasing the level of use of innovative activity allows enterprises in the building materials industry not only to develop economically, but also to improve the methods of organizing the construction process. The construction industry is currently experiencing a period of transition from infrastructure facilities and industrial projects to residential and commercial real estate. This is due to the rapid urbanization. In particular, global spending on residential and commercial real estate construction is expected to increase by approximately \$ 17 trillion between 2021 and 2025. Particular attention should be paid to the issues of correct assessment and effective management of innovative activities of enterprises in the building materials industry.

Besides that, in the context of globalization of the world economy, scientific research is conducted to study and assess the level of innovative activity of enterprises in the building materials industry. Formation of the level of innovative activity of enterprises in the building materials industry, its quantitative assessment, systematization of various theoretical and methodological approaches in this regard, development of an integrated development system taking into account the unique features of the industry, organization of economic activities of enterprises.

Enterprises in the building materials industry and the development of these enterprises. The study of the management of innovative activities as a result of economic activity, improvement of the scientific and methodological foundations for assessing and managing innovative activities, further improvement of the competitive environment of enterprises in the building materials industry is one of the tasks of the priority areas of this scientific research. Particular attention is paid to the effective use of high innovative activity as the main factor of economic success in the organization and management of modern enterprises in the building materials industry of Uzbekistan. An enterprise that effectively manages its innovative activities and successfully brings various innovations to the market will have high competitive advantages.

The tasks associated with paying sufficient attention to the management of the economic activities of enterprises in the building materials industry of Uzbekistan and improving the practice of managing the innovative activities of economic entities are defined. Effective implementation of these tasks requires theoretical and methodological improvement of the concept of "innovative activity", organization of clusters of construction materials enterprises creating a chain of added value from raw material extraction to its processing, finished construction and production of finishing materials, innovative development of a comprehensive system for assessing the coefficient of production of innovative products, the coefficient of costs for innovation, the coefficient of profitability of innovative products, the coefficient of costs for scientific research and study, workers and employees with academic degrees, the index of innovative efficiency, patent and licensing indicators. Increasing the volume of activity requires scientific research aimed at developing forecast indicators until 2028 based on a multifactor model built on the basis of effective means of increasing the innovative activity of economic processes at enterprises in the construction materials industry.

This study was carried out according to the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 11, 2023 regarding "Strategy of Uzbekistan 2030", PD-60, dated January 28, 2022 "Development of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PR-5544 dated September 21, 2018 "On approval of the strategy for innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021", PR-6119, dated November 27, "Modernization, advanced and innovative development of the construction industry for 2021-2025", PD-3698, dated May 7, 2018 "Improving the mechanisms for implementing innovations in the industry and economic sectors", PD-4335 dated May 23, 2019 "On additional measures for the advanced development of the building materials industry" and other regulations related to this area.

Certainly, the research to a certain extent meets the objectives specified in the regulatory legal documents. The building materials industry is an important sector of the economy, without which it is impossible to imagine modern construction. This sector is one of the main branches of heavy industry. The industry is gaining importance in connection with the production of materials necessary for the construction of various facilities, including residential and commercial buildings, infrastructure facilities and industrial complexes.

Definitely, the building materials industry is a branch of industry that produces building materials for housing, industry, agriculture and construction. The building materials industry is closely related to almost all sectors of the economy. With the increase in the volume of construction of factories and plants, houses, roads and irrigation facilities, the need for building materials also increases. The building materials industry consists of several sub-sectors, each of which specializes in the production of certain types of products. These are as follows:

1. Cement industry. Cement is the main component of concrete and is widely used in construction. Modern cement production is highly automated and uses environmentally friendly technologies, such as dry grinding and low-emission cement mills.

2. Concrete industry. Concrete is the main material for the construction of foundations, walls, ceilings and other structural elements of buildings and structures. Modern technologies make it possible to produce concrete with various properties, including strength, frost resistance, water resistance and other properties.

3. Brick industry. Brick is a classic material for building walls. Modern technologies allow producing brick from various materials, including clay, sand concrete and ceramics. There are

different types of brick: solid, hollow, faceted, ceramic, sand-lime, etc., which differ in size, shape, color, properties and price.

4. Production of wall panels. Wall panels are designed for fast and efficient construction of walls. They are made from various materials, including concrete, wood, plasterboard, metal and others.

5. Production of roofing materials. Roofing materials provide protection for buildings from precipitation. Modern roofing materials differ in different colors, shapes, properties and durability. The most popular types include tiles, metal tiles, slate, ondulin, roofing felt, waterproofing membranes.

6. Gravel production industry. Gravel and crushed stone are used as fillers for concreting, road construction, landscaping and other purposes.

7. Insulation materials industry. Thermal insulation materials are used to insulate buildings, which reduces heat loss and lowers heating costs. The most popular types of thermal insulation materials include mineral wool, expanded polystyrene, polystyrene foam, ecowool, etc.

8. Dry mix construction industry. Dry mix construction is a powdered material that can be diluted with water and used for a variety of construction tasks, including plastering, stucco, masonry, tiling, and more.

Besides that, the development of the construction materials industry is closely linked to innovation. Modern technologies make it possible to produce high-quality, highly durable, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective materials. The production of new types of materials with improved properties is also rapidly developing, which makes it possible to implement bolder and more modern construction projects. In general, the construction materials industry plays a key role in economic development, providing housing, industrial facilities, infrastructure, and other important possibilities.

There are approaches to assessing the innovative activity of enterprises in the construction materials industry based on various criteria, which include assessing innovative activity from different angles. Below is a summary of the main methods and criteria.

1. Creation of innovative products and provision of services. The level of introduction of new products or services by an enterprise to the market is studied. It is assessed by the level of updating or modernization of existing products.

2. Innovation processes. At the same time, the introduction of new technologies and production processes are innovations aimed at increasing the efficiency and profitability of production processes.

3. Investments and financial indicators: the volume of investments directed to innovation activities and funds spent on innovation activities, and their share in the volume of total expenses.

4. Research and development: the enterprise's research and development activities and their results, as well as the number of patents received by the enterprise and the number of licensed technologies.

5. Human capital and personnel qualifications: the qualifications and experience of personnel involved in innovation activities, the availability of training and advanced training programs aimed at increasing innovation activity.

6. The market and level of competitiveness. In this case, increasing the competitiveness of an enterprise in the market through innovations evaluates the market share achieved through innovative goods and services.

7. Cultural and social factors. This can be done by assessing the presence of innovative thinking and culture at the enterprise and the impact of innovation on society and the environment.

Based on these criteria, various methods have been developed to assess innovation activity. By applying this methodology to their activities, enterprises will be able to determine the level of innovation activity and make strategic decisions aimed at increasing it.

It is important to suggest that N.M. Rasulov, one of the economists of our country, defined the concept of innovation activity as follows: "Innovation activity is the process of transforming scientific knowledge into innovations, transforming them from innovative ideas into specific products, technologies or services, process events that are distributed through changes and use". At the same time, this scientist presented the following formula for determining the level of innovation activity.

$$IFD = (QUT / HIT)$$

IFD - the level of innovation activity.

QUT - the value of high-tech products.

HIT - expenses incurred for ITTKI.

At present time, in order to assess the innovative activity of enterprises, it is first necessary to assess the innovative potential. However, issues related to the assessment of innovative activity and innovative potential of business enterprises are still debatable. Here it should be said that, according to the definition of Yu.A. Lapteva, innovative processes are the innovative potential of an enterprise, which is the main link in the economic system, demonstrating its ability to modernize and renew, and determines its technical leadership and superiority. In the theory of innovation, three types can be distinguished as its components. This is the general innovative potential: resources, production and internal potential are manifested as an economic category.

1. Coefficient of production of innovative products. To calculate the share of innovative products in the total volume of production, the following formula is used.

$$I_m = M_i / M_t$$

Here: I_m is the share of innovative products;

M_i is the volume of innovative products;

M_t is the volume of gross output.

2. Share of innovative costs. In this case, the following formula is used to calculate the share of innovative costs in total costs. $I_c = C_i / C_t$

Here: I_c – coefficient of expenses on innovation;

C_i – expenses spent on innovation activity;

C_t – volume of total expenses.

3. Advantage of innovative products. The following formula is used to calculate the profit from innovative products.

$$I_p = (P_i - C_i) / (P_t - C_t)$$

Here: I_p – coefficient of profit received from innovative products;

P_i – total income from innovative products;

C_i – expenses spent on innovation activity;

P_t – total income from product sales;

C_t – volume of total expenses.

$$IN_f = (I_m * I_c * I_p * S_c * I_{L_{ul}} * I_e * P_l)^{1/7}$$

On the basis of this formula, a common single value of the enterprise's innovative activity is created, and this indicator determines the economic state of the enterprise and the possibility of economic development. In conclusion, it can be said that a single indicator should be used to express the innovative activity of an enterprise in the construction materials production industry, and through this indicator it is necessary to have an idea of the general indicator of the economic development of the enterprise.

Moreover, based on the study of the theoretical development, content, composition and role of innovative activity in improving the efficiency of the enterprise, the following conclusions can be made.

The author's definition of the concept of "innovative activity" as the most important criterion for the effective organization and evaluation of innovative activity of enterprises in the building materials industry has been developed. In our opinion, innovative activity of an enterprise is the process of creating and implementing innovations as a result of qualitative and quantitative changes in the indicators of innovative activity based on human capital. Innovative activity of enterprises in the building materials industry is the creation, implementation and development of new ideas, technologies, products or services by an organization or an individual. In this process, in addition to creating innovations, it is also important to bring them to the market and commercialize them. Innovative activity serves to increase the competitiveness of the organization and strengthen its position in the market. This is manifested in the ability of an enterprise in the building materials industry to meet the needs of consumers through the production of finished construction products under the influence of the external environment, to ensure long-term sustainable development of an enterprise in the building materials industry based on the efficient use of available resources.

According to the methodological approach, the innovative activity of enterprises in the building materials industry is considered as the creation, implementation and development of new ideas, technologies, products or services by an organization or person as a result of qualitative and quantitative changes in the indicators of innovative activity based on human capital; in our opinion, it is necessary to have a single standard coefficient that determines the innovative activity of the enterprise. It is possible to determine this indicator, which means that all indicators that make up innovative activity are expressed through a common integral coefficient.

$$IN_f = (I_m * I_c * I_p * S_c * I_{L_{ul}} * I_e * P_l)^{1/7}$$

Based on this formula, a common single value of the enterprise's innovative activity is created, and this indicator determines the economic state of the enterprise and the possibility of economic development.

Additionally, a single indicator should be used to express the innovative activity of an enterprise in the construction materials production industry, and through this indicator it is necessary to have an idea of the general indicator of the economic development of the enterprise. The processes of globalization and integration, tightening of competition rules contribute to the creation of a single economic space on a global scale. Geopolitical changes give rise to new changes and improve production and technology centers. In this process, each enterprise is faced with the need to maintain its position, otherwise it will simply be washed away by the wave of history. In today's troubled world, innovation plays a key role. It allows enterprises to quickly adapt to changes, find new markets, create competitive advantages and increase profits. Therefore, increasing the innovative activity of enterprises is one of the main factors of their success. However, talking about innovations is not enough. It is important how they are used in practice. To do this, it is necessary to build a bridge between different sectors of the economy, including

science, production, education and society. Scientific research creates the basis for innovation by discovering new technologies and approaches. Production turns these discoveries into real products and services. Education prepares qualified specialists who are able to implement innovative ideas.

By summarizing it should be suggested that society creates conditions for the development of innovations, their financing and stimulation of entrepreneurial activity. Therefore, the study of fundamental and practical aspects of increasing the innovative activity of enterprises is becoming one of the main tasks of the modern world. This task requires a comprehensive approach, including the creation of an effective system of financing innovative projects, the development of research infrastructure, improving the quality of education and training of specialists in the field of innovation, stimulating entrepreneurship and creating a favorable environment for the development of innovative startups.

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